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ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE FOURTH SECTOR: ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS AND SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODELS (Springer, 2021)

Marisa R. Ferreira (*ESTG, Politécnico do Porto, Portugal*)¹

Alexandra Braga (*ESTG, Politécnico do Porto, Portugal*)²

Entrepreneurship in the Fourth Sector is a book by five internationally renowned researchers with a wide range of quality publications: María Isabel Sánchez-Hernández, Luísa Carvalho, Conceição Rego, Maria Raquel Lucas, and Adriana Noronha. They collected various contributions through a research network on entrepreneurial ecosystems and sustainable business models.

Part One comprises five chapters underlining the importance of the fourth sector and the role it can play. A conceptualization of the fourth sector is presented and we can clearly frame the fourth sector under different forms of sustainable business models, active citizenship and collaborative societies. These five chapters present robust arguments based on a well-built methodology and provide us a comprehensive overview about how the fourth sector affects and shapes new entrepreneurial ecosystems. This part provides examples and new approaches through innovative experiences and the relationship with public policies and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); and, in the end, we can find generational characteristics and their relationship with new social entrepreneurship ideas. It is worth noting that, aside geography, the complex and challenging reality is transversal, as well as the recommendations presented.

Part Two emphasizes the importance and centrality of social innovation. The authors demonstrate how discussing social innovation theoretical framework, sharing discussions through different case studies, and raising awareness, building resilience, acquiring new competences and even autonomy and independence are central to the potential growth of social innovation. Some of these chapters present very specific contexts that draw the reader's attention to different formats and realities through cooperatives or alternative food networks, thus increasing the presence of newfound voices. Generally, we can find new business models, the combination of entrepreneurial sustainability with other goals, such as social or economic goals, generating a positive impact and more sustainable communities.

Part Three presents future trends, as well as some complementary approaches. Some of these chapters discuss the role of companies and profits; the approaches are very interesting and encourage debate, public awareness and the sharing experiences, and promote deeper reflections. The examples cited, such as the fashion industry, activist companies or the problems raised by an increasing aging population, have contributed to rising attentiveness and empowerment, challenging – and possibly transforming – our understanding of future sustainable paths.

¹ Centro de Inovação e Investigação em Ciências Empresariais e Sistemas de Informação, R. do Curral, 4610-156, Felgueiras, Portugal, mferreira@estg.ipp.pt, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4194-9127>

² Centro de Inovação e Investigação em Ciências Empresariais e Sistemas de Informação, R. do Curral, 4610-156, Felgueiras, Portugal, abraga@estg.ipp.pt, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7548-9785>

This book presents an expanded assessment on a topic that is not only new, but also contains many uncertainties. It provides a set of different viewpoints regarding conceptualization, hybrid models, and innovative developments. In general, the arguments and contributions presented in the book are multifaceted but well systematized and allow readers to effortlessly follow the key arguments. The three parts are organized around different subjects, which is helpful for the reader. All the authors have a wide-ranging knowledge on the case studies presented, and the editors were able to publish a solid and well-articulated book.

Sánchez-Hernández, M.I; Carvalho, L.; Rego, C.; Lucas, M.R. and Noronha, A. 2021. *Entrepreneurship in the Fourth Sector: Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Sustainable Business Models*. Springer. 356 pp. ISBN 978-3-030-68390-0 (eBook). ISBN 978-3-030-68389-4.